

Kinetic Studies in the Mechanism of Micellar catalysed Oxidation of Monoaminomonocarboxylic Acids by Chloramine-T in Acidic Medium

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Kinetic investigations of the oxidation of monoaminomonocarboxylic acids (i.e. glycine and alanine) by chloramine-T (CAT) have been made in presence of cationic surfactant cetyl trimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) in the acidic medium. The rate shows a first order dependence on oxidant concentration but is fractional in case of the substrate concentration. Ionic strength and presence of the added halide ions have no effect on the rate, but a positive effect of Hg^{2+} ions is noted

The reactions were studied at different temperatures and the values of activation parameters have been computed

THE rate of a chemical reaction may be modified by the presence of micellar aggregates in the system under reaction. The investigation of micellar catalysis has provoked a great interest, since the study might provide a basic model for the interpretation of some aspects of enzymatic catalysis¹. Structural similarities between globular proteins and spherical micelles are that they have hydrophobic cores with polar groups on their surfaces. The structures of micelles are disrupted by common protein denaturing agents, such as urea and guanidinium salts. Both catalytic micelles and enzymes bind substrates in a non-covalent manner; and the kinetics of micellar catalysis resemble that of enzymatic catalysis in that the micelles may be saturated by the substrate.

Experimental

All solutions were prepared in double-distilled water and the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade². Distilled acetic acid was used.

Kinetic runs: Requisite amount of the substrate, surfactant, acid solutions and water (to maintain the total volume constant for all the runs), were taken in glass-stoppered bottles painted black from outside to avoid any photochemical reaction and were thermostated at 25°. A measured amount of CAT solutions at the same temperature was added to the mixture and progress of the reaction was followed by iodometric estimation of the reaction mixtures at various time intervals³.

Stoichiometry: In the stoichiometry study, the reaction mixture containing excess of CAT was allowed to react with the amino acids at 25° in the presence of acetic acid and surfactant for 24 h. The unreacted CAT was estimated in the system. The estimated value showed that one mole of glycine and

alanine consumed one mole of CAT giving aldehydes and ammonia. Ammonia present in the reaction mixture was quantitatively estimated by the microkjeldahl procedure. Aldehydes were detected by preparing their 2,4-DNP derivatives and checking the m.p. *p*-Toluene sulphonamide was the major product among the reaction products.

Results and Discussion

Dependence of rate on [Oxidant] and [Substrate] When the amino acids are in large excess, the plots of $\log(a-x)$ vs time are found to be linear, indicating first order dependence on CAT⁴. The pseudo-first order rate constants in chloramine-T calculated at different initial concentrations of the reactants are found to be independent of the substrate concentrations. Hence the reaction follows fractional order behaviour with respect to the amino acids concentrations (Table 1).

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF REACTANT CONCENTRATION ON RATE OF OXIDATION OF AMINO ACIDS BY CAT

[CAT] $\times 10^{-3}$ mol dm ⁻³	[Amino acid] $\times 10^{-2}$ mol dm ⁻³	$k \times 10^2 \text{ min}^{-1}$	
		Glycine	Alanine
2.0	5.0	1.37	1.35
2.5	5.0	1.38	1.30
3.0	5.0	1.34	1.33
3.5	5.0	1.33	1.34
4.0	5.0	1.39	1.37
4.5	5.0	1.36	1.38
4.0	2.0	1.66	1.08
4.0	2.5	1.62	1.13
4.0	3.0	1.60	1.17
4.0	3.5	1.50	1.23
4.0	4.0	1.44	1.27
4.0	4.5	1.42	1.32
4.0	5.0	1.39	1.37

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Dependence of rate on surfactant concentrations : The reaction was studied at different concentrations of the surfactant (Table 2). The plots of k vs [surfactant] depicts a curve with a maximum (Fig. 1). The rate of reaction increases with the increase of CTAB and then decreases with the increase of CTAB

Fig. 1 Plots of k vs [CTAB]: (O) glycine and (Δ) alanine

concentration⁵. This behaviour is in agreement with the micellar catalysis of organic molecular type. It has been observed that the Stern layer of the micelle increases rapidly with increasing concentration of CTAB and organic substrate relatively. This could be well understood from the results of the rate enhancement of the reaction with CTAB concentration.

TABLE 2

[CATB] $\times 10^3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ $\times 10^5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ *	$k \times 10^2 \text{ min}^{-1}$	
	Glycine	Alanine*
0.0	0.45	0.87
0.5	0.96	0.94
1.0	1.24	1.26
1.5	1.39	1.37
2.0	1.27	1.36
4.0	1.24	1.30
6.0	1.15	—

*For alanine surfactant concentrations

Dependence of rate on mercuric acetate concentration : The reaction was studied at various concentrations of the scavenger. It is observed that the reaction rate increases with the increase in the concentration of the scavenger, which may be due to the formation of a more active oxidising species. In the presence of mercuric acetate the reaction is found to be first order in [CAT].

Effect of the solvent on reaction velocity : The rate was studied at different concentrations of the solvent (Table 3). It is observed that the rate decreases in both the cases, with increasing concentrations of methanol. The effect of varying solvent

composition on the reaction velocity has been discussed in detail by Amis and others⁶.

TABLE 3

Methanol %	$k \times 10^2 \text{ min}^{-1}$	
	Glycine	Alanine
5	1.48	1.46
10	1.35	1.33
15	1.28	1.26
20	1.20	1.11
25	1.16	1.15
30	1.04	1.05

Within the given range (5–30%) studied no significant observation can be made regarding the effect of solvent. There is a very small but regular decrease in velocity constant with increasing concentration of alcohol resulting in regular decrease in the value of dielectric constant.

Effect of halides : Addition of chloride and bromide ions to the reaction mixture has no significant effect on the rate. Hence in this case Orton rearrangement, involving organic haloamides, was not applicable.

Effect of ionic strength : The reaction rate was not influenced by the addition of chemically neutral salts. Hence the ionic behaviour of slow step in the reaction mechanism is ruled out. The reactions were studied at different temperatures and the values of activation parameters are computed (Table 4).

TABLE 4

Activation parameters	Glycine	Alanine
E_a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	52.2	25.1
ΔH (kJ mol ⁻¹)	49.6	22.1
ΔS (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	25.1	48.2
ΔG (kJ mol ⁻¹)	82.4	85.1

Reaction mechanism : On the basis of the experimental results, the following probable rate laws are proposed.

We know that in this case, oxidation proceeds by two paths i.e. (i) in the absence and (ii) in the presence of the surfactant⁷.

(i) In the absence of the surfactant :

After appropriate substitution, we get the following equation,

$$\frac{-d[\text{CAT}]}{dt} = \frac{kWK[\text{CAT}][\text{S}]}{1+k[\text{S}]} \quad (1)$$

(ii) In the presence of surfactant :

where, D_n is the most abundant micellar species with aggregation number n . Step (2) represents

the association of substrate with the micellar species which is oxidised by CAT in the step (3) forming the *p*-toluene sulphonamide among the products. After approximation, the final expression is

$$k_{obs} = \frac{kW + kS KD [D_n]}{1 + kD[D_n]} \quad (4)$$

where, k_{obs} is the pseudo-first order constant,

$$k_{obs} = \frac{-d[CAT]}{dt} \cdot \frac{1}{[CAT]} \\ = \frac{2.303}{t} \log \frac{[CAT]_0}{[CAT]}$$

Increasing concentration of surfactant increases the rate constants sigmodally to a plateau beyond which there is no more rate enhancement. This behaviour is the consequence of substrate-destabilisation-stabilisation in the polar environments of the aggregates. The association of molecules is governed by hydrophobic and electrostatic interactions. The longer the hydrocarbon chain on a molecule (amino acid), the greater is the extent of its incorporation in a cationic micelle (CTAB).

As the hydrocarbon chains of amino acid molecules are incorporated into the micelles, the carboxyl groups of the amino acid which are oriented towards the solution phase start getting easily nonhindered manner by the oxidant (CAT) molecules, consequently the rate of reaction increases.

It is well-known that in aqueous solutions chloramine-T forms different oxidising species such as *p*-toluene sulphonamide, RNCl, RNHCl⁻ ions, RNCl₂ and HOCl species depending on the acidity of the medium. The species RNCl₂ formation is ruled out as the process is first order dependent with respect to CAT. Hence the species RNHCl and HOCl are more probable in the acidic medium and they are responsible for the amino acid oxidation. Amino acids are known to exist as cation and zwitterion in the acidic medium and considering the latter one as the reactive species, the following schemes has been proposed for the oxidation of amino acid at lower acidic concentration range.

(I) In the absence of surfactant :

Ionic strength of the medium has no effect on the rate, indicating that neutral species are involved in the rate-determining step. The formation of HOCl takes place in a slow step through the hydrolysis of RNHCl followed by rapid protonation and interaction with the substrate. The retardation of rate by the added methanol could indicate the dipole-dipole nature of reactants and it supports step (2) of the scheme.

The activation energy value is highest for the slowest reaction and vice versa, indicating that it is enthalpy controlled⁸. The negative ΔS^\ddagger values indicate the formation of the activated complex with a reduction in the degree of freedom of molecules, whereas the fairly high positive and the near constancy of the values of ΔG^\ddagger show the operation of similar mechanism for the oxidation of both the amino acids by CAT. It has been also suggested that the transition state is highly solvated.

Theoretical and thermodynamic treatment of micellar effect: The present kinetic results have been applicable on the basis of Piszkiwicz. In this model substrate (*s*) and *n* molecules of detergent (*D*) aggregates to form the catalytic complex (*D_nS*) which then reacts to form the product.

The observed rate constant k_{obs} can be expressed as a function of the detergent concentration (*D*) by equation (1) which on rearrangement gives equation (2),

$$k_{obs} = \frac{k_m[D]^n - k_0 K_D}{K_D + [D]} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{or } \log \left(\frac{k_{obs} - k_0}{k_m - k_{obs}} \right) = n \log D - \log K_D \quad (2)$$

where, k_0 and k_m are the rate constants in the absence and presence of surfactant aggregates, K_D is the dissociation constant of the catalytic complex (*D_nS*) and *n* the index of cooperativity. A plot of $\log (k_{obs} - k_0)/(k_m - k_{obs})$ vs $\log D$ is linear with a slope *n* and intercept $-\log K_D$ which justifies the applicability of this model⁹. The values of cooperativity index (*n*) in the case of glycine and alanine are found to be equivalent to unity.

Fig. 2. Plots of $\log [D_n]$ vs $\log (k_{obs} - k_0)/(k_m - k_{obs})$.

In case of CTAB, it has been found that the CMC value of the surfactant increases with the increase in the amino acid concentration. The formation of the so-called iceberg structure around the hydrocarbon chains of surfactants brings about a loss of entropy after their dissolution. We know that the amino acids are generally water structure makers. In the case of CTAB micelle the head groups are strongly hydrated in character and decrease the electrostatic interaction between the head groups and the counterions. Under such situation, the CMC of CTAB increases when the amino acid concentration is increased.

Thermodynamic studies give much more informations about dynamic nature of the molecules or ions present in solutions. Assuming that the aggregation number and the degree of ionisation of the surfactants are independent of temperature, the standard enthalpy (ΔH_m°) and standard entropy (ΔS_m°) of micellisation are evaluated from the temperature dependence equations of CMC.

Regarding the thermodynamic parameters, in the case of cetyltrimethyl ammonium bromide, it is observed that ΔG_m° values of micellisation become more and more negative with gradually increasing concentration of amino acid and hence more stable becomes the micelle. The approximate enthalpy of micellisation is exothermic and more negative.

The decrease in ΔS_m° values with increasing concentration of amino acid indicates an increase in the orderliness of the CTAB-H₂O-amino acid system.

References

1. E. J. FENDLER and J. H. FENDLER, *Adv. Phys. Org. Chem.*, 1970, **8**, 271; J. H. FENDLER and E. J. FENDLER, "Catalysis in Micellar and Macromolecular Systems", Academic, New York, 1975; E. H. CORDES, "Reaction Kinetics in Micelles", Plenum, New York, 1973; K. L. MITTAL, "Micellization, Solubilization and Microemulsions", Plenum, New York, 1977, Vol. 2
2. E. F. DUYNSTEE and E. GRUNWALD, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **81**, 4540, 4542
3. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 3rd ed., ELBS, London, 1961, p. 370.
4. P. ALEXANDER AND G. GOUGH, *Biochem. J.*, 1951, **48**, 504; I. STANKOVIC and J. VESTKO, *Chem. Zvesti*, 1960, **14**, 434; A. KANTOUCH and S. H. ABDEL-FATTACH, *Chem. Zvesti*, 1971, **25**, 222
5. E. J. FENDLER, C. L. DAY and J. H. FENDLER, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1972, **76**, 1460.
6. E. S. AMIS, "Solvent Effects of Reaction Rates and Mechanisms", Academic, New York, 1966
7. V. S. SRINIVASAN, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sci.)*, 1982, **91**, 241.
8. R. D. GILLION, "Introduction to Physical Organic Chemistry", Addison-Wesley, London, 1970, p. 168; R. BRUCE and E. H. CORDES, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **89**, 4695.
9. PISZKIEWICZ and DENNIS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **99**, 1550